

Enhanced Security with Quantum Key Distribution and Blockchain for Digital Identities

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Abstract—As evolving digital ecosystems become increasingly interconnected and reliant on digital transactions, secure, private and user-centric identity solutions are garnering more spotlight than ever before. In this paper, we propose an innovative architecture that integrates quantum key distribution (QKD) with blockchain-based self-sovereign identity (SSI) systems for secure key distribution and network/user management for mobile networks with advanced 6G network capabilities. The proposed approach leverages the advanced security guarantees of QKD to ensure the confidentiality and integrity of communications and uses the decentralized and immutable nature of blockchain technology to give individuals/organizations control over their digital identities in mobile environments. We then go on to expound on the foundations of architectural components and discuss its implications for various telecom specific services and applications. Finally, we present challenges and future directions to provide quantum communication support against future digital threats and a decentralized framework for identity management with the global pursuit of more privacy-friendly and user-centric digital services, and offer comparisons with traditional approaches.

Keywords—quantum key distribution, blockchain, network management, self-sovereign identity.

I. INTRODUCTION

Conventional encryption methods such as RSA and Elliptic-Curve Cryptography (ECC) are based on the computational difficulty of problems such as factoring large prime numbers or solving discrete logarithms. However, quantum computers could potentially solve these problems in polynomial time, which makes these methods insecure [1]. Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) represents a paradigm shift in secure data communications. It utilises the principles of quantum mechanics to enable two parties to generate a shared, secret, random key known only to them, which can then be used to encrypt and decrypt messages [2]. The importance of

QKD for secure communication arises from its fundamental difference to conventional cryptographic methods. QKD is secure against attacks from quantum computers because its security hinges upon the principles of quantum physics rather than computational complexity. One of the unique features of QKD is its inherent ability to detect eavesdropping. QKD also provides forward secrecy, i.e. even if a future breach compromises the encryption keys for subsequent communications, past communications remain secure. This is because a new quantum-generated key can be used for each communication session, which is not derived from previous keys. While QKD requires specialized equipment, it can be integrated into existing fiber optic networks (leveraging the particle nature of light), making it a viable option for improving the security of critical infrastructure communications. However, QKD nodes are normally authenticated with pairwise shared keys. While this approach is suitable for a small number of nodes, it is not readily transferable to high-density long range networks, which could include connections without quantum-enabled hardware (repeaters etc.), e.g. over very long distances or wireless connections [3].

At its core, blockchain technology is a decentralized ledger that records transactions across multiple computers in a way that ensures the security, transparency and immutability of data. Its features make it suitable for a wide range of applications, including identity management, which has become an important area of interest especially with the concept of Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) [4]. Blockchain-based SSI solutions empower individuals by giving them control over their own identity information and allowing them to securely share only what they need with the people they choose. This decentralized approach not only enhances privacy and security, but also fosters interoperability between different platforms and services. Identity management, on the other hand, has been predominantly centralized, leaving control in the hands of third parties and exposing users to the risk of identity theft and privacy breaches.

In this paper, we describe a tentative architecture in detail where QKD is integrated with Blockchain Network (BCN)-

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based SSI and several other layers for 6G networks. The integration of QKD into the architecture introduces an extra layer of security that is theoretically immune to various future advancements in computing, including quantum computing, by ensuring the secure distribution of encryption keys using the principles of quantum mechanics. Blockchain-based SSI, on the other hand, shifts the paradigm of identity management from a centralized model to a decentralized one where users have full control over their digital identities, enhancing privacy and security. Taken together, this novel architecture provides a holistic approach that is not only more secure and user-centric, but can also support the next generation of telecommunications requirements and set a new standard for privacy, security and efficiency in the digital age.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

Quantum Key Distribution mechanism: QKD is a cryptographic technique that uses quantum mechanics to secure communication channels by distributing encryption keys between two parties in a secure and verifiable manner. QKD relies on the principles of quantum mechanics, such as the uncertainty principle and the no-cloning theorem, to ensure the security of the key exchange. A wide range of research exists on the topic of QKD solutions. Since the introduction of the first QKD protocol, BB84, in 1984 [5], a variety of operational QKD protocols have been proposed by some companies (both commercial and government) to secure communication systems. In [6], four different methods for interconnecting today's remote European QKD networks in metropolitan areas are proposed. A reference architecture with functional elements and reference points relevant for the control and management of the QKD network (QKDN) is contained in the document ITU-T Y.3804 [7]. The authors in [8] study the challenges and opportunities in quantum information and communication technologies (QICTs).

Secure key distribution with blockchain infrastructure: Blockchain is a distributed ledger technology that enables secure and transparent recording through decentralized consensus mechanisms. Blockchain can provide a tamper-proof and verifiable record of key transactions, ensuring transparency and accountability in the key management process. QKD can be used to establish secure communication channels between mobile devices and blockchain nodes that ensure the confidentiality and integrity of key exchanges [9], [10]. The blockchain infrastructure can record QKD key exchange transactions, providing an immutable record of key distribution events. The blockchain's immutable ledger ensures that key management transactions, including key generation, distribution and revocation, are securely recorded and tamper-proof. Smart contracts can automate key management processes and enforce predefined rules and policies for key generation, access control and revocation. The decentralized architecture of the blockchain eliminates the need for central points of trust and thus reduces the risk of single points of failure and unauthorized access to keys. For this reason, participants in the blockchain network, including mobile devices and identity issuers, validate and verify key management transactions together via consensus

mechanisms.

QKD with blockchain networks for authentication: If QKD is used in blockchain networks, it can significantly improve the security and privacy of SSI systems. By securely exchanging keys between the parties involved in a transaction, QKD can increase the security of identity verification processes and make it nearly impossible for attackers to intercept or forge identity transactions on the blockchain. These networks would also be resistant to potential attacks from quantum computers and would secure the blockchain infrastructure against future technological threats and ensure the longevity and reliability of SSI systems. For authentication, in [11] an experimental realization of a quantum secure blockchain platform is proposed that uses quantum key distribution over an urban fiber optic network for secure authentication. The authors of [3] integrate Post Quantum Cryptography (PQC) and QKD for an authenticated hybrid key exchange protocol for an information-theoretically secure architecture. Furthermore, the PQC-based approaches have also been recommended for 5G/6G systems recently [12], [13]. However, these solution focuses on securing quantum keys with blockchain networks and does not provide a detailed multi-layered approach for 6G networks.

III. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Fig. 1 shows a multi-layered architectural approach that integrates QKD, Software Defined Networking (SDN), Management and Orchestration (MANO) platforms, key management systems, blockchain-based SSI and application layers. Each layer has different functions and interacts with the others to ensure secure, efficient and scalable operation. In proposed architecture, (i) *the quantum layer* lays the foundation for secure communication by providing quantum-safe keys that are managed by the key management layer. Components include quantum transmitters and receivers, quantum channels (fibre optic or free space) and QKD protocols. The quantum layer interfaces with the key management layer to provide secure keys for encryption and decryption processes. (ii) *The control layer*, which is managed by the management and orchestration layer, abstracts the control plane from the network hardware to enable more flexible network management and configuration and optimizes network resources and paths for both key distribution and data traffic. The SDN controller enables centralized control of network traffic, facilitating the implementation of security policies and the dynamic management of network resources. The components include the SDN controller software, southbound APIs (for communication with the quantum layer and network devices) and northbound APIs (for communication with the management and orchestration layer). This layer manages the network paths for the distribution of quantum keys and conventional data streams, optimizing network performance and security.

(iii) *The MANO layer* orchestrates resources across the virtual and physical infrastructure, including compute, storage and network components. It automates the provisioning and management of network services and functions. It consists of MANO platform, Virtual Network Function (VNF) Manager,

Fig. 1: Different layers of secure communication for 6G networks.

Network Function Virtualization (NFV) Orchestrator [14]. It coordinates with the control layer to enforce policies and with the application layer to ensure that resources are allocated efficiently for applications such as real-time video transmission. (iv) *Key management layer* manages the lifecycle of the keys provided by the quantum layer, including their generation, distribution, storage, rotation and deletion, and ensures that they are managed securely and in compliance with policy. It has a key management system (KMS) and secure key storage as components. It receives secure keys from the quantum layer and distributes them to the identity layer for encryption/decryption processes and to the application layer.

(v) *The identity layer* ensures secure and user-controlled identity management through blockchain technology. It provides a secure and decentralized framework for managing digital identities and uses blockchain technology to ensure immutability, transparency and user control over identity data. Its components are blockchain ledgers, smart contracts for identity verification with SSI principles and digital wallets for storing identity credentials. It uses keys from the key management layer for secure transactions and interactions within the blockchain network and provides authentication services for the application layer. Finally, (vi) *the application layer* provides services such as real-time video streaming or VoIP transmission leveraging the security, efficiency and scalability enabled by the underlying layers. It supports end-user applications that require real-time secure data transmission

by leveraging underlying security layers, identity verification and network optimization. It utilises secure communication channels established by the lower layers for the transmission and reception of encrypted video data, relies on the identity layer for user authentication, and benefits from the dynamic network management provided by the control and MANO layers.

A. Identity Layer

The identity layer as detailed in Fig. 2, especially in the context of BCN-based SSI systems, is designed to give users control over their digital identities while ensuring security, privacy and interoperability. This layer consists of several key components, including issuers, users (holders), verifiers, decentralized identifiers (DIDs) and the blockchain ledger itself. Each of these components plays a crucial role in the identity verification process, with their interaction facilitated by the immutable and transparent nature of blockchain technology. Blockchain ledger serves as the decentralized backbone of the SSI system and records transactions and DIDs in a secure, tamper-proof manner (e.g. using Hyperledger Indy or Spruce ID). It ensures that all identity credentials can be verified without relying on a central authority. DIDs are used to create verifiable digital signatures and can be resolved into DID documents containing public keys and other authentication details. Issuer is the entity that creates, signs and issues digital credentials to the user. Users receive digital credentials

from issuers, store them in their digital wallets and present them to verifiers when required. Verifiers may be services or organizations that require proof of identity or other credentials for access or transactions.

Fig. 2: Identity layer with internal interactions between its components and interactions between the layers.

B. Quantum and Key Management Layers

The packet exchanges involved in QKD module is presented in Fig. 3. The steps explanation of how QKD works:

(1) Preparation of Quantum States: The sender (i.e., Alice) prepares a sequence of quantum particles, typically photons, in specific quantum states, such as polarized photons or photons in superposition states. Alice sends these prepared quantum states to the receiver (i.e., Bob) over a communication channel, which could be a fiber optic cable or free space transmission. Upon receiving the quantum states, Bob measures certain properties of the particles. The measurement basis (e.g., polarization direction) is chosen randomly for each particle.

(2) Exchange of Information: Alice and Bob then publicly communicate (over a classical channel) the basis they used for each measurement, but not the measurement results themselves. Alice and Bob compare the bases they used for each measurement. If they used the same basis, they keep the corresponding measurement result as a potential part of their shared key. If they used different bases, they discard that measurement result.

(3) Shared Key Generation: Finally, Alice and Bob obtain a shared secret key that they can use for secure communication. The security of this key is guaranteed by the laws of quantum mechanics, as any attempt by an eavesdropper to intercept or measure the quantum states would be detectable.

IV. SERVICES, APPLICATIONS AND CASE STUDY

The proposed architecture, which combines QKD, BCN-based SSI and additional layers for control, management and application deployment, has far-reaching applications and services in the context of a 6G network. In cross-sector applications, quantum-safe blockchain networks could extend SSI applications beyond traditional sectors to areas such as healthcare, education and government services, where identity security and privacy are of paramount importance. For example,

Fig. 3: Quantum Layer Operations.

the secure and private exchange of medical records, credentials and certificates could be facilitated without compromising patient privacy. To increase security, telecom service providers can provide voice and video communication services that are protected against eavesdropping, including quantum computing threats, by using QKD for key distribution. With end-to-end encryption based on quantum-safe keys and identity verification through blockchain-based SSI, messaging services can also guarantee privacy and data integrity, promoting secure personal and business communications. For IoT and smart cities, 6G's ability to support a massive number of connected devices, combined with QKD and SSI, can ensure secure and efficient IoT networks, which are crucial for smart city infrastructures, from traffic management to energy distribution. In addition, a blockchain-based SSI can provide secure and manageable identities for IoT devices, enabling secure device-to-device communication and autonomous device authentication. For emergency services, 6G networks can facilitate real-time information sharing, while QKD and SSI ensure the security and integrity of communication between responders. The enhanced security features offered by QKD-integrated SSI systems could also help meet stringent regulatory requirements for data protection and privacy by offering solutions that respect the principles of data sovereignty and user consent.

Case Study: Consider that two users want to start a private conversation via their 6G-enabled smartphones. Both users have digital identities that are managed via a blockchain-based SSI system and ensure control over their personal data and authentication processes. Before communication begins, both users verify each other's identity using their blockchain-based SSIs. This process verifies each other's digital credentials without revealing unnecessary personal information, which is facilitated by the transparency and immutability of the blockchain. Once identity verification is complete, a secure communication channel is established with QKD over the 6G network. QKD enables both users to exchange a secret encryption key, which ensures that the communication cannot be intercepted or decrypted by unauthorized parties, including those with access to quantum computers. With the secure key, users can now encrypt their communications (voice, video or text) end-to-end. The high-speed and low-latency properties of the 6G network ensure that the encryption and decryption processes take place in real time and without any noticeable delay for users. Hence, the combination of QKD and blockchain-based SSI within a 6G infrastructure provides a level of security and privacy that is virtually unbreakable even by future quantum computers. Users have full control over their

identity and personal data, which significantly improves data protection and security in telecommunications. Finally, the inherent capabilities of 6G networks, such as high bandwidth and low latency, ensure that the additional security measures do not affect the quality or speed of communication.

V. CHALLENGES AND LIMITATIONS

Table I compares conventional identity management systems with QKD-integrated blockchain-based SSI systems in terms of various features.

A. Scalability, performance and interoperability

The integration of QKD with BCN-based SSI systems poses some technical challenges due to the fundamental differences in technology, scalability performance and interoperability. Despite its promising capabilities, QKD faces challenges in the form of distance limitations and the need for trusted relay nodes over long distances, as well as the high cost of implementation. QKD also faces scaling issues when integrating with blockchain technology, as it relies on distributed ledgers for consensus and requires frequent and fast transactions across a potentially global network. The high resource requirements of QKD systems, including the need for specialized hardware and the challenge of maintaining quantum states over long distances, collide with the decentralized and often resource-constrained environments in which blockchains operate. To ensure the quantum resilience of blockchain cryptographic algorithms without compromising on speed and efficiency, while leveraging the secure key distribution mechanism of QKD, novel solutions are needed, especially in terms of data minimization, user consent and cross-border data transfer, to connect these fundamentally different technologies.

B. Security and Privacy

The integration of QKD and BCN-based SSI technologies must also consider regulatory, security and privacy issues associated with SSI systems designed to give individuals control over their identity. Adapting QKD for broader, more scalable use while maintaining security guarantees is a major technical hurdle. Developing middleware or frameworks that can seamlessly integrate QKD and BCN-based SSI technologies without compromising their respective strengths is also critical. Ensuring end-to-end security in BCN-based SSI applications involves protecting data at rest, in use and in transit. This means not only that the key exchange must be secured, but also that the stored identity data on the blockchain and during processing must be protected, which may require additional cryptographic techniques. Even with QKD, other aspects of blockchain technology may remain vulnerable to quantum computing attacks. The development of quantum-resistant algorithms for all aspects of blockchain security is an ongoing challenge. In terms of privacy, while SSI aims to give users control over their identity data, the integration of QKD raises questions about the management and access control of cryptographic keys.

C. Quantum threats

Quantum computing poses a significant threat to blockchain technology, primarily through its potential to break the cryptographic algorithms that underpin blockchain security. Current blockchain systems rely heavily on cryptographic techniques such as public key cryptography to secure transactions and create digital signatures that are theoretically vulnerable to quantum attacks. The ability of the quantum computer could allow an attacker to forge digital signatures and thus steal cryptocurrencies, alter the blockchain or double-spend transactions. In addition, quantum computers could potentially decrypt previously recorded blockchain transactions and thus jeopardize the confidentiality of historical data if it has been encrypted using quantum-prone algorithms. Another potential threat is the consensus mechanisms used by blockchains. For example, Bitcoin's proof-of-work (PoW) mechanism could be jeopardized if quantum computers can solve cryptographic puzzles much faster than classical computers. This would lead to a concentration of mining power and undermine the decentralized nature of the blockchain. To counter these threats, quantum-resistant cryptographic algorithms, also known as post-quantum cryptography need to be developed and deployed [15], [16]. However, there are a number of challenges in implementing these new algorithms including the technical difficulties of integrating new cryptographic methods without disrupting existing systems and services.

D. Regulatory and standardization hurdles

The regulatory framework for quantum technologies and blockchain is still evolving in many countries. The lack of clear regulations can lead to uncertainty for companies looking to deploy these technologies, particularly in sectors that handle sensitive personal data, such as finance and healthcare. For SSI systems, regulators are keen to ensure privacy, security and compliance with data protection laws such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in Europe. The lack of global standards for QKD and interoperability of blockchain systems is another major hurdle. Standardization is critical to ensure that the technologies work seamlessly across different platforms and jurisdictions. In addition, the integration of QKD with blockchain for SSI applications requires standards that cover the unique aspects of this integration, such as the secure exchange of quantum keys across blockchain networks.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

This paper presented an innovative multi-layered architecture that integrates QKD, BCN-based SSI and the upcoming 6G network technologies to address the critical challenges of digital identity management in terms of security, privacy and user control. Through our detailed investigation of the system architecture, including the identity, quantum and key management layers, as well as potential services, applications and case studies, we have investigated the feasibility and transformative potential of our proposed solution in the context of modern digital ecosystems. The combination of QKD and blockchain can indeed provide enhanced security and privacy for self-sovereign identity in mobile networks, protect against

TABLE I: Comparison between traditional identity management systems and QKD-integrated, blockchain-based SSI systems

Feature	Traditional Identity Management Systems	QKD Blockchain Based SSI
Security	— Moderate to High where Centralized model is vulnerable to single point of failure.	— Very High since distributed ledger technology, eliminates single point of failure
Privacy	— Varies with implementation, but often relies on third-party control over user data, potentially compromising privacy	— High, as it allows individuals to own and control their identity without the need for a centralized authority, enhanced by quantum-secure communications.
User Control	— Generally low to moderate, as users must rely on third parties to manage and safeguard their identity information.	— Very high, as it empowers users with full control over their digital identities, including what information is shared and with whom.
Interoperability	— Moderate since it often requires complex integrations or standardizations to work across different systems and networks. — Limited interoperability between different identity providers	— High since blockchain technology provides a standardized approach that can support various identity systems and services, facilitating interoperability.
Scalability	— High, centralized systems can be efficiently scaled, though at the risk of increasing the central point of failure.	— Moderate to high, scalability can be a challenge due to the computational and bandwidth requirements of QKD and the consensus mechanisms of blockchain
Infrastructure Complexity	— Moderate, depends on the scale and architecture of the system, with centralized databases and authentication systems.	— High, due to the need for specialized quantum cryptography hardware for QKD and the distributed nature of blockchain networks.
Quantum-Resistance	— Low, most traditional systems use cryptographic methods that are vulnerable to quantum computing attacks	— Very high, as QKD provides a quantum-secure method for key distribution, making it resistant to quantum computing threats.
Implementation Cost	— Moderate, primarily software-based costs, with existing infrastructure potentially leveraged — Relatively lower cost to implement and maintain	— High, due to the need for quantum cryptography hardware and the development of new blockchain platforms or adaptation of existing ones.
Regulatory Compliance	— High, established systems often have clear regulatory frameworks and compliance mechanisms in place.	— Varies, as emerging technologies like QKD and blockchain may face uncertain regulatory environments, requiring adaptation as laws evolve.
Decentralization	— Low, relies on centralized entities for management and control, creating potential bottlenecks and single points of failure.	— Very high, inherently decentralized, distributing control across the network and reducing reliance on any single entity.
Identity Management	— Relies on centralized identity providers	— Enables self-sovereign identity management

quantum-based attacks and ensures control over personal data. In addition, users retain ownership of their cryptographic keys and enable secure authentication, access control and data sharing without relying on centralized identity providers. We also discuss the challenges and limitations and compare the proposed approach with conventional identity management systems.

In the future, new methods of identity verification and authentication, including quantum-safe digital signatures and zero-knowledge proofs that improve privacy and security in online transactions, may be used when systems with inbuilt mechanisms involving combination of QKD and blockchain technologies are available.

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